

**FLEXURAL BEHAVIOR OF POST-TENSIONED CONCRETE FILLED FRP TUBE FOR
WIND TURBINE TOWER APPLICATIONS**

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the potential application of post-tensioned concrete-filled FRP tubes (CFFT) for wind turbine towers. A 5.8 m tall hollow core CFFT tower with a tapered profile (base and top diameters of 533 and 417 mm, respectively) was tested experimentally; first under free vibration conditions, followed by cyclic loading under concentric and eccentric lateral loads, and finally under monotonic loading to failure. The tower failed in flexure near the base as a result of GFRP tube rupture. Preliminary results suggest that CFFTs can be a promising alternative to conventional wind turbine tower systems, offering transportability, durability, and tailorable structural characteristics.

KEYWORDS

Wind turbine tower; concrete-filled FRP tube; CFFT; static; dynamic; GFRP.

INTRODUCTION

Previous research studies have extensively explored concrete-filled fibre-reinforced polymer (FRP) tubes (CFFTs) for structural applications such as flexural and axial loading in bridges and other structures (Fam & Rizkalla, 2001; Fam et al. 2003; Fam & Mandal, 2006; Hadi et al., 2016; Mohamed & Masmoudi, 2010; Ozbakkaloglu & Vincent, 2014). Additionally, CFFTs have proven to be effective in utility poles (Mitchell & Fam, 2010) and have exhibited excellent performance under dynamic impact loading (Qasrawi et al., 2015). This successful performance of CFFTs can be extended to wind turbine towers, where the demand for sufficient flexural stiffness to limit deflections is crucial.

One common method for constructing concrete towers is with prestressed concrete. This involves introducing tensioning elements, such as steel rods or strands, into the concrete structure and prestressing them. Although prestressed concrete structures are relatively more expensive due to the additional tensioning elements, they offer a higher load-bearing capacity compared to reinforced concrete. Moreover, by adjusting the prestressing level, the stiffness can be enhanced within certain limits (Hau, 2006). In the case of concrete wind turbine towers, prestressing is employed to improve serviceability performance, such as crack and deflection control (Mandal & Fam, 2006; Grünberg & Göhlmann, 2013).

When considering the construction of concrete wind turbine towers, the inclusion of a glass fibre-reinforced polymer (GFRP) tube at the outer circumference introduces a new parameter. This addition has the potential to significantly enhance the constructability and structural performance of small-scale wind turbine tower systems that may be appropriate for remote off-grid areas. GFRP tubes are lightweight, easy to transport and erect, and corrosion resistant. The tapered profile also facilitates a segmental construction process for towers of varying height, and post-tensioning can provide continuity and enhance flexural stiffness (Watfa et al., 2018). In this study, preliminary results are presented from an experimental program investigating the flexural performance of a 5.8 m tall cantilevered post-tensioned hollow core CFFT tower segment under lateral loading.

Conventional wind turbine towers are made of steel tubes or concrete as shown in Figure 1. Lattice towers are less suitable for remote areas since they require more regular maintenance. Steel tubular towers have excellent strength and ductility but have a short service life of only 20 years since they are

susceptible to corrosion and are expensive to maintain. In contrast, concrete towers provide an extended lifespan range from 40 to 60 years, offering a more durable solution for long-term use. Concrete towers are also more stable against buckling. However, concrete towers are heavier than steel tubular towers, requiring a larger footing, and require steel reinforcement as they are weak in tension. Drawbacks of conventional wind turbine towers include their high cost, transportation challenges, and long-term durability (de Lana et al., 2021; Veljkovic et al., 2011).

To avoid these weaknesses, CFFTs present a potential alternative that can be easily manufactured and transported to the site. In addition to acting as a permanent formwork for the concrete, the external FRP lightweight tube guarantees that CFFTs have high tensile strength and are appropriate for flexural loading. Furthermore, GFRP tubes are light in weight and thus less energy is required to transport them to construction sites in remote areas. Moreover, the GFRP tubes are resistant to harsh weather conditions and corrosion attack, which means a reduction in maintenance costs and increased life span.

Figure 1: (a) Steel tubular tower (Veljkovic et al., 2011), (b) Concrete tower (ACCIONA, n.d.), (c) Steel lattice tower (Veljkovic et al., 2011)

Limited studies have been conducted on FRP wind turbine towers. Polyzois et al. (2009) conducted an experimental and numerical study on segmented GFRP wind turbine towers that involved testing scaled 4.88 m towers in cantilever configuration. The towers consisted of multi-cell sections made of filament wound cells connected with resin. The test program included phases for ultimate strength, compression, static and dynamic loading. The results showed slip between the tower and the base and additional deflection at the tower's tip. The towers also underwent dynamic vibration testing. Finite element models were compared with experimental results, showing good agreement. The study concluded that the presence of an elastic jointed connection did not affect the tower's dynamic performance.

Although CFFTs have not previously been tested for wind turbine applications, a number of studies have reported excellent flexural performance. Fam et al. (2003) tested full-scale precast CFFT composite piles under four-point bending. The moment-curvature response, ultimate moment capacity, cracking moment, and slip between the concrete core and the FRP tube were observed. The study also included modeling the stress-strain relationship and conducting lateral tests. The results showed the effect of cracking, stiffness changes, and the benefits of prestressing.

In another study, Fam and Rizkalla (2001) studied concrete-filled hollow tubes under axial and axial-flexural loading. They found that using GFRP tubes improves concrete confinement, leading to increased strength and ductility. Fully filled tubes provided the highest level of confinement, while the presence of a central hole reduced the confinement effect. However, adding an inner tube can enhance the confinement effectiveness for this type of structure.

St. Onge and Fam (2021) conducted a study on the torsional behavior of circular CFFTs. They tested hollow GFRP tubes and CFFTs in pure torsion. The lateral confinement provided by the FRP tube significantly increased the strength and ductility of the concrete, resulting in a 250% increase in the ultimate torque compared to the hollow tubes. The twist angles of the CFFTs were also improved, with near-cross-ply and angle-ply tubes showing a 14% and 45% improvement, respectively. The failure of

the specimens was brittle, starting with the rupture of the FRP tube followed by local crushing of the concrete core. The presence of an internal concrete hole had little effect on the torque-twist response of the CFFT but improved the strength-to-weight ratio by 21%. However, the lack of internal restraint led to a decrease in the maximum torque and twist by 12% and 20%, respectively, due to concrete crushing.

To the best of the authors' knowledge, no previous research studies have reported on the performance of tapered CFFT tower segments.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

Tower fabrication

Commercially available GFRP tubes used for telecommunication poles were used in this study. These tubes have a tapered profile allowing them to be joined together in the field using an overlap splice connection (Watfa et al., 2018). The tower segment presented in this study was 5800 mm in height, with a base diameter of 533 mm and a top diameter of 417 mm. GFRP tubes with ten plies of ply configuration = $[\pm 4^\circ, \pm 30^\circ]_s$ were used with an average thickness of 10 mm for the GFRP tube (as manufactured by RS Poles). The manufacturer reports the ultimate tensile strength and elastic modulus as 205 MPa and 20.1 GPa, respectively.

The tower was reinforced with four 15M (16 mm) steel bars longitudinally and 10M (11.3 mm) closed steel ties laterally, as illustrated in Figure 2. The spacing of the first nine ties near the base of the tower, which is crucial for bearing stress distribution, was set at 120 mm, and the remaining ties were spaced at 350 mm along the height of the tower. To maintain a uniform concrete cover of 25.4 mm (1 inch), plastic spacers were mounted along the four longitudinal reinforcement bars. Circular steel plates, 19 mm thick, with holes for the longitudinal rebar and steel tendons, were connected to the top and bottom reinforcing cages of each tower (Figure 2). These plates aimed to distribute the prestressing load and improve the axial bearing capacity of the concrete section. A 3 mm galvanized wire was wrapped around both ends of each conduit to resist spalling stresses at the anchorage zone.

Figure 2: Reinforcement configuration (left) and cage fabrication (right)

Thirty strain gauges were installed along the four longitudinal reinforcing bars: 20 gauges on the tension and compression bars (A and B), and 10 gauges alternately placed on the two mid-depth bars (C and D). For bars A and B, six gauges were installed at 250 mm spacing starting at a height of 200 mm from the tower base, while the remaining four gauges were spaced at 1000 mm intervals. The same spacing pattern was followed for bars C and D, with gauges installed in alternating positions. All strain gauges were 6.35 mm long and were tested with a voltmeter before and after assembly to ensure their functionality. Once verified, the instrumented reinforcement cages were placed inside the GFRP tubes for concrete casting.

Tapered sonotubes (cardboard tubes) were used to create the hollow core (Figure 3). Each sonotube was cut longitudinally and re-rolled to achieve a constant taper slope of approximately 1% along its length to match the outer slope. The diameters of the sonotubes were measured at 350 mm intervals during the

rolling process to ensure the desired taper shape. Plastic ties and nails were used to secure the overlapped layers, and excess overlap was trimmed at an angle matching the taper shape to maintain a constant 100 mm overlap.

The tower specimen was cast vertically using the GFRP tube as a stay-in-place form, as shown in Figure 3. The steel cage was positioned vertically, and the GFRP tube was placed over it using an overhead crane. Styrofoam sheet was placed under the base of the tower for stability and to prevent concrete leaking. Lumber was used to secure the top and bottom of the specimen. Fine sand was used as a filling material inside the sonotube to prevent its inwards buckling during concrete pouring, and was removed after the concrete hardened. Ready-mix self-consolidating concrete with a compressive strength of 61.6 MPa was poured through the top openings of the tower. After the concrete cured and reached the desired strength, a post-tensioning system was introduced. Each of the four tendons was stressed to approximately 1000 MPa and locked with prestressing wedge anchors. Two diagonally opposite tendons were stressed simultaneously to ensure uniform stress distribution in the concrete. A high-strength grout of 75 MPa with a water-to-cement ratio of 0.4 was mixed and injected into the conduit ducts to facilitate bond transfer between the prestressing strands and the concrete.

Figure 3: Preparation of CFFT segments for casting

A heavily reinforced reusable concrete foundation was constructed to secure the towers during testing. It consisted of two parts with a hexagonal hole in the middle (Figure 4). The dimensions of each part were 870 mm long and 1740 mm wide, with a depth of 790 mm. The depth of the foundation was determined based on the model developed by Sadeghian and Fam (2010) to predict the critical embedment length for CFFT towers and reinforced concrete footings. The foundation units were anchored to the floor using high-strength bolts. The tower was placed vertically inside the hexagonal opening of the foundation using an overhead crane. High strength grout of 82 MPa was used to fill the empty space between the circular tower and the hexagonal opening, as well as the 90 mm height/gap at the base of the column created by the extension of the prestressing wedges plates and barrels. The extension of the prestressing barrels and the grout underneath the tower created a strong footing to resist the torsional moment at the base of the column during eccentric loading. Once the grout had properly cured, the two foundation units were clamped together horizontally at four points using 50.8 mm diameter high-strength bolts.

Test setup

A steel reaction frame was anchored to the strong floor of the laboratory using 64 mm diameter high-strength bolts (Figure 4). The loading setup included an MTS hydraulic actuator of 1000 kN capacity and 500 mm stroke. A clamping system was added 900 mm below the top of the tower that provided five possible configurations to connect the actuator to apply loads at various eccentricities. The external UV-protective coating layer of the tower was sanded off at the clamping area and covered with epoxy to increase friction and prevent slipping under eccentric load. Cable transducers were connected to the tower at various locations to measure displacement in the in-plane and out-of-plane directions, as well

as sliding and uplift of the foundation block. Additional strain gauges were also mounted to the outer surface of the FRP tube in the longitudinal and hoop directions. The tower segment prior to testing is shown in Figure 5.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4: (a) Reusable foundation block and (b) test setup

Figure 5: CFFT tower segment prior to testing

Test procedure

The test was comprised of four stages:

Stage 1: Free vibration test: A high strength cable connected to a winch was used to exert a pulling force on the top free end of the tower. A notched rectangular steel plate was designed as a “fuse” with one side connected to the winch and the other side connected to the top free end of the tower. The steel plate was specifically engineered to rupture when subjected to a force of 30 kN. This intentional rupture allowed the tower to experience free flexural vibrations under the applied force as it is released.

Stage 2: Cyclic flexural testing under concentric loading: The tower was subjected to a series of gradually increasing reversed loading cycles (push and pull) corresponding to approximately 10%, 15%, 20%, and 25% of the theoretical failure load. Each load increment was repeated for three cycles.

Stage 3A and 3B: Cyclic flexural-torsional testing under eccentric loading: Wind turbines are commonly designed to rotate on the top of their towers to harness wind energy from various directions, which can lead to torsional moments in the tower structure due to friction. The loading cycles from Stage 2 were repeated with eccentricities of +559 mm and -559 mm.

Stage 4: Monotonic flexural test to failure under concentric loading: The actuator was repositioned in line with the center of the tower and load was gradually increased at a rate of 9 mm/min until failure occurred.

RESULTS

Stage 1: Free vibration test

The displacement vs time plot from the free vibration test is presented in Figure 6. The fundamental period of vibration (T_d), averaged over the first three cycles, was approximately 0.176 seconds corresponding to a damped natural frequency of vibration of about 5.69 Hz for the free-standing tower (Table 1). Additionally, the average damping ratio ζ , determined by Equation 1 and 2 was found to be around 9%. Damping is important for structures because it determines how well they can absorb and dissipate energy during vibrations. In wind turbine towers, high damping is especially crucial to reduce

fatigue damage and ensure safety. The tower's vibration test results reveal a significant improvement in the damping ratio compared to the study conducted by Polyzois et al. (2009). This high damping ratio is a favorable characteristic because it signifies the tower's capability to effectively withstand wind-induced vibrations. The results of the vibration tests demonstrate that prestressed CFFT towers can possess good dynamic characteristics for wind turbine tower applications in remote areas. However, more research is needed to optimize the design of these towers and their dynamic characteristics to reduce the effects of wind-induced vibrations on the turbine and tower. Although the relatively high damping ratio implies good capacity to dissipate energy, reducing the risk of potential damage or failure, it is important to note that this result is for only one portion of an actual wind turbine tower and thus the overall dynamic characteristics of the installed system will be different in terms of both natural frequency and damping. Nevertheless, the relatively high damping ratio for this component bodes well for an actual CFFT wind turbine tower to have more damping than a tower constructed from components with less inherent damping.

$$\delta = \ln \frac{x(t_{n0})}{x(t_{n1})} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

$$\zeta = \frac{\delta}{2\pi} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

Table 1: Damping values and frequency results of the tested tower

tn #	Amplitudes x(tn)	tn (s)	Td	Frequency (Hz)	$\zeta = (\delta/2\pi)$
0	29.9540	10.689			
1	19.0450	10.865	0.176	5.6818	0.072075
2	11.3030	11.043	0.178	5.6180	0.083037
3	5.5320	11.216	0.173	5.7803	0.113719

Figure 6: Tower free vibration response

Stage 2: Cyclic testing under concentric loading

The load vs. time and load vs. top deflection from Stage 2 are plotted in Figure 7. The response was almost symmetrical under push (positive force) and pull (negative force) loading, and demonstrated mainly linear elastic behavior with limited hysteresis. The center cyclic loading reached approximately 83% of the cracking load, which aligns with the expected behaviour for loads below 40% of the ultimate capacity, highlighting the tower's serviceability. The maximum displacement at a service load of approximately 60 kN was about 80 mm in both directions, or about 1.5% of the tower height, which is close to the proposed service limit of 1.25% proposed by Nicholson (2011).

(a)

(b)

Figure 7: Cyclic loading response: (a) load vs time and (b) load vs top deflection

Stage 3: Cyclic testing under eccentric loading

The tower response under left side and right side eccentric loading were very similar; therefore, results are only presented for the right side eccentric load (Figure 8). Overall, the response was similar to that observed under concentric loading, except that the maximum force was slightly less for the same extension of the actuator (57.0 kN vs. 62.5 kN) due to the slight twisting of the loading clamp, and the response was slightly unsymmetric (57.0 kN for push cycles vs. 49.7 kN for pull cycles). The behavior remained essentially elastic in both directions.

Figure 8: Eccentric loading response: (a) load vs time and (b) load vs. top deflection

Stage 4: Test to failure

The load-deflection response of the tower for Stage 4 (monotonic loading to failure) is shown in Figure 9. The response was fairly linear up to approximately 140 kN (240 mm), followed by a slight decrease in stiffness up to the peak load. Failure was initiated by GFRP rupture on the tension side of the tower near the top of the foundation block at an applied load of 182 kN and displacement of 361 mm. The cracking load, estimated to be approximately 77 kN, represents about 42% of the failure load. This finding highlights the CFFT tower's ability to withstand a substantial portion of the failure load before cracks appear. Similarly, the yield load, measured at around 105 kN, accounts for approximately 58% of the failure load. These results demonstrate the strength and resilience of the material or structure under the applied loads. Strain gauge data suggests that the steel reinforcing bars at the tension and compression sides near the top of the foundation block yielded prior to FRP rupture. The maximum strains measured in the FRP tube were 7083 $\mu\text{mm}/\text{mm}$ in compression, 9362 $\mu\text{mm}/\text{mm}$ in tension, and 234 $\mu\text{mm}/\text{mm}$ in the hoop direction. The peak load was followed by a series of load drops as the displacement continued to increase. The test was eventually stopped after the actuator reached its maximum stroke capacity. The ultimate displacement reached during the test was 522 mm with a corresponding force of 115 kN (37% below the peak load). Photos of the tower after failure are shown in Figures 10 and 11.

Figure 9: Monotonic load-deflection response

Figure 10: CFFT tower at ultimate displacement (left) and after unloading (right)

Figure 11: FRP tensile rupture above the foundation block (left) and rupture surface shown after removal from foundation propagating towards tower base (right)

CONCLUSIONS

The results of a large scale experiment for a cantilevered post-tensioned CFFT tower with a tapered profile is presented in this study. The following preliminary findings can be drawn:

- The CFFT tower tested in this study demonstrated high damping (9%) which can reduce vibration-induced fatigue damage (although further research is needed to optimize behavior and consider different tower geometries and the effect of turbine mass).
- The response of the tower under reversed cyclic loading up to 40% of the expected failure load was essentially linearly elastic with limited hysteresis. The maximum displacement reached during this testing stage was about 1.5% of the tower height which is larger than the proposed serviceability limits of 1.25% for conventional wind turbine towers.
- Under eccentric loading, the tower stiffness (measured as the load-to-lateral displacement ratio at the maximum applied service load) was reduced by 1.5% compared to the stiffness measured under concentric loading.
- The flexural failure of the CFFT tower was governed by the tensile capacity of the FRP tube. Due to the internal steel reinforcement and post-tensioned tendons, significant post-peak displacements can be reached with considerable residual moment capacity.
- CFFT towers present a promising alternative for wind turbine towers in remote areas due to their transportability, durability, and good structural characteristics that can be tailored to meet specific service criteria.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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